

THE IMPORTANCE OF A UNIVERSAL CONVENTION AGAINST CYBERCRIME BY THE UNITED NATIONS: RUSSIAN APPROACH

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Abstract: This article explores the ongoing international discussions and debates surrounding the idea of a universal convention against cybercrime, often referred to as a "cybercrime treaty". It highlights several key points regarding the significance of such a convention under the auspices of the United Nations (UN). The article acknowledges the challenges of reaching consensus on the terms of a universal cybercrime convention due to differing legal traditions, interests, and concerns about potential misuse for political or censorship purposes. It mentions Russia's advocacy for a treaty within the UN Open-Ended Working Group on Security of and in the Use of Information and Communications Technologies (OEWG) and highlights the historical background of negotiations on international cyber governance. The article concludes by emphasizing the importance of monitoring developments related to the potential convention's implications on accountability and digital human rights, especially regarding the balance between security and human rights.

Keywords: Universal convention, cyber security, OEWG, UN, legal framework.

The idea of a universal convention against cybercrime, often referred to as a "cybercrime treaty," is a topic of ongoing discussion and debate within the international community. While there is general agreement on the need to address cybercrime at the global level, reaching a consensus on the specific terms and provisions of such a treaty has proven challenging. Here are some key points to

consider regarding the importance of a universal convention against cybercrime by the United Nations:

1. **Global Nature of Cybercrime:** Cybercrime is a global problem that knows no borders. Criminals can launch cyberattacks from one country, target victims in another, and hide their activities in a third. A universal convention can provide a framework for international cooperation in investigating, prosecuting, and preventing cybercrime.
2. **Harmonization of Legal Frameworks:** Different countries have varying legal frameworks for addressing cybercrime. A universal convention can help harmonize these frameworks by establishing common definitions, procedures, and penalties for cybercrime offenses. This can facilitate extradition and cooperation among nations.
3. **Improved International Cooperation:** Cybercrime often involves cross-border elements, making it difficult for any single country to combat effectively. A convention can enhance international cooperation by setting out guidelines for information sharing, joint investigations, and mutual legal assistance.
4. **Legal Gaps:** The digital age has presented new challenges that existing legal frameworks may not fully address. A universal convention can help fill gaps in existing international law and adapt to evolving cyber threats.
5. **Protection of Human Rights:** While addressing cybercrime is crucial, it is equally important to ensure that efforts to combat cybercrime respect human rights, including privacy and due process. A convention can include provisions to safeguard these rights while combating cybercrime.
6. **Deterrence:** The existence of a universally accepted convention can act as a deterrent to cybercriminals, knowing that their actions will be met with a coordinated international response.
7. **Capacity Building:** Many countries, particularly developing nations, may lack the resources and expertise to effectively combat cybercrime. A convention can

include provisions for capacity building and technical assistance to help countries strengthen their cybersecurity and law enforcement capabilities.

8. Public-Private Collaboration: A convention can encourage public-private collaboration in combating cybercrime. The private sector often plays a critical role in identifying and responding to cyber threats.

However, it's important to acknowledge that reaching consensus on the terms of a universal cybercrime convention can be a complex and time-consuming process. Different nations have different legal traditions, interests, and priorities, which can make negotiations challenging. Additionally, concerns about potential misuse of such agreements for political or censorship purposes have been raised.

Efforts to develop such a convention have been ongoing, and there have been regional agreements, such as the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime, that address some aspects of cybercrime. While the journey towards a universal convention may be ongoing, the importance of international cooperation in combating cybercrime remains widely recognized.

Recent years United Nation's platform is taking significant steps towards it. The UN Open-Ended Working Group on Security of and in the Use of Information and Communications Technologies (OEWG) serves as a platform for discussions on international cybersecurity. The process was initiated by Russia as an alternative to the UN Governmental Group of Experts, which also dealt with cybersecurity issues but consisted of a selected group of countries. Since 2019, delegates of UN member states within the OEWG have been sharing their perceptions of current and emerging cyber threats, discussing ways to build cybersecurity capacity, establish confidence-building measures, and understand the application of international law to cyberspace. Throughout these discussions, Russia has consistently advocated for the establishment of a treaty[1]. It's also important to recognize that this submission is only the initial step, and further discussion and negotiation will be required before any action is taken.

How it all started?

In the United Nations (UN), important negotiations aimed at regulating the activities of states and non-state actors in cyberspace began in the late 1990s. The late 1990s, when access to and use of Internet had become, commonplace, physical-world conflicts triggered many state-targeted cyberactions, primarily conducted by non-state actors. [2] Despite increasing awareness, particularly in recent years, these discussions have remained largely obscure to wider audiences although their outcome can have wide-ranging consequences for both governments and nongovernmental stakeholders, as is the case with governance regimes in other policy areas. Equally important, at least two very different visions for governance in cyberspace have emerged and are competing for votes among UN members. Like-minded states mainly from the Global North advocate an open, free and secure cyberspace that preserves the free flow of information globally, while another group led by Russia and China strive to establish a governance regime that would enable greater government control of cyberspace.[3]

Russia presented the first draft resolution “Developments in the Field of Information and Telecommunications in the Context of International Security” in 1998[4], which for the first time fixed the “triad of threats” in the field of ICTs security: the use of ICTs for purposes incompatible with the maintenance of international stability and security and the use of ICTs for criminal or terrorist purposes.

Recently, in October 2017, The Russian Federation presents a letter to the UN General Assembly containing a draft of the United Nations Convention on Cooperation in Combating Cybercrime, intended for circulation to Member States. [5]

According to russian PhD in history A.V. Krutskikh the document was especially relevant in the context of the growing arms race, the emergence of the possibility of using ICTs in military affairs. In 1996, the United States Department

of Defense prepared the Doctrine for Command and Control Warfare (Joint Pub 3-13.1 Command and Control Warfare, DOD US, 1996), followed by the Joint Doctrine of Information Operations in 1998. The strategic task of such operations was to influence the enemy's military-political leadership to make a decision that would be favorable to the initiator of the attack, or to disable the infrastructure of the opponent. In order to maintain national security, the United States and a number of other countries soon started to transform the structures of their armed forces and established special cyber units. In 1999, the resolution was updated and for the first time noted the possible negative impact that ICTs could have on security in both the civil and military spheres.⁸ Despite the fact that the Russian draft resolution became the subject of heated discussions and two different approaches (Russian and American) to information security issues were outlined, Russia presented an updated version of the draft resolution at the 54th session of the UN General Assembly in late 1999 that included threats related to the use of ICTs in the civil and military spheres.[6]

However, the Russian view of the system of universal security is not approved by all states and parties. Some subjects are very cautious about Russian proposals: in January 2021, Human Rights Watch raises alarms that UN member states are beginning the process for a cybercrime treaty whose "champions are some of the world's most repressive governments...the initiative raises serious human rights concerns." [7]

The submission of Russia's vision for a Convention of the UN on Ensuring International Information Security is certainly a development to keep an eye on. It is important to consider the potential implications of such a convention, especially on accountability and digital human rights.

In the opening paragraphs Russia contends that a legally binding treaty is needed as there are gaps in current international law. But many states (e.g. Sweden, South Korea, Colombia, Austria, and the United States) agree that there are no such gaps,

and only further clarification of existing international law is needed. All countries have for instance agreed to the applicability of the UN Charter (a binding legal treaty) to cyberspace.

While the document refers to human rights and fundamental freedoms, it merely elaborates on the freedom of expression and calls for the possibility of it being restricted for national security, public order and moral reasons. The mentioning of human rights is counterbalanced with security language.

When it comes to capacity building the Russian concept paper argues that this should be done under UN auspices, adding that there could be public-private partnerships. This framing shows that Russia prefers intergovernmental efforts over public-private collaborations that have been streamlined through organizations such as the Global Forum on Cyber Expertise.[8]

As we continue to monitor the developments in the international cyber governance landscape, including Russia's proposal within the UN, it's crucial to strike a balance between security imperatives and the protection of digital human rights. The international community must work collaboratively to find common ground, establish a framework that can adapt to evolving cyber threats, and ensure that the convention serves as a force for global cybersecurity while upholding fundamental rights and freedoms. Ultimately, the importance of international cooperation in combating cybercrime remains undeniably vital, and the pursuit of a universal convention is a significant step toward achieving this goal.

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